

“CD-ROMs in Print”: Transmediality in Early Digital Culture

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In the late 1980s and early 1990s an era of “new media” opened, full of the promises of multimedia. This was a time when databases emerged as the new “symbolic form” (Manovich, 2002), museums turned “virtual,” and interactivity became a buzzword. Our paper revisits this history¹ through one “transmedia” and “boundary” object: *CD-ROMs in Print* books.

While CD-ROM culture is traditionally framed—and often self-described—in terms of *multimedia*, defined by the integration of diverse media forms within a single digital framework (Schafer, 2022), *CD-ROMs in Print* catalogs complicate this narrative. These catalogs, which provide extensive listings of published CD-ROM titles, offer a distinctive lens through which we can explore the shifting boundaries between and across different media forms.

We first position the catalogs as products of media circulation, emphasizing their role as transmedia objects. Situated at the crossroads of print and emerging digital cultures (Rassuli, Tippins, 1997), these “transmedia remnants” offer an opportunity to explore the transition from analog to digital media, their intertwinement and complementarity. Our analysis then focuses on the production of CD-ROMs, the wide range of actors involved, and the reconfiguration of media players, as captured in the catalogs. Finally, we examine the CD-ROM titles and their content descriptions, that reveal the many ways in which transmediality manifests within the medium.

1. CD-ROMs in Print as a transmedia object

CD-ROMs in Print were extensive catalogs designed to list, classify, and describe all available CD-ROM titles of the time. These catalogs or “directories” began to be published almost immediately after the emergence of CD-ROM technology and saw multiple editions from the late 1980s to the early 2000s².

The 1998 edition, which forms the basis of this study, describes itself as offering “unparalleled access to CD-ROMs produced, distributed, and sold internationally, as well as within the United States” (Suchowski, 1998, vi). This gateway to the “new digital world” took the form of a traditional printed book. In both its name and purpose, *CD-ROMs in Print* mirrored *Books in Print*, printed catalogs that had long served for tracking published books. Before the rise of digital databases, *Books in Print* was an essential tool for librarians, researchers, booksellers, and publishers, helping them to locate book titles and compile bibliographies. *CD-ROMs in Print* can be viewed as a continuation and adaptation of these established practices to a new technological medium. Ironically, while *CD-ROMs in Print* was published predominantly as traditional printed catalog³, *Books in Print* was among the first resources

¹ Within the framework of the conference and its core theme, we chose to focus on these printed books. However, this study is part of a larger project, CD-Hist, which uses a variety of historical sources—including company archives, specialized and general press, CD-ROMs, web archives, advertising, and oral histories. The project aims to revisit the history of CD-ROMs while also engaging with its extensive born-digital heritage.

² *CD-ROMs in Print* was one of several printed CD-ROM catalogs. Other examples include the CD-ROM Directory (1987–1996), the Optical Publishing Directory (1987–1991), and the CD-ROM Librarian Index. *CD-ROMs in Print* was published from 1987 to 2004, with earlier editions produced by Meckler (1987–1998) and later by Gale (1998–2004).

³ *CD-ROMs in Print* was also published in CD-ROM format, but significantly later than *Books in Print*—beginning in 1992. The print edition, however, was never discontinued.

to transition to the CD-ROM format (p. 100). The CD-ROM editions of *Books in Print*, launched in 1987, demonstrated the medium's potential to store data and function as a searchable database and was positioned as a revolutionary alternative to traditional paper catalogs (Clarck, Bingham, 1987).

CD-ROMs were praised as a “transient technology” (McSean, Law, 1990), predicted to replace print by consolidating multiple volumes into a single compact disc. Yet, paradoxically, CD-ROM culture also contributed to the proliferation of paper: the 1998 edition of *CD-ROMs in Print* alone spanned nearly 1,500 pages. This paradox captured by Dominique Boullier and Catherine Charlier in their observations about the Internet (“While the Internet may not yet drive sales online, it certainly sells a lot of paper”, 1997, 167) may also apply to CD-ROMs.

While rooted in paper and book culture, *CD-ROMs in Print* also reflects the emerging digital database culture of its time, as well as the development of a broader digital culture. This is evident both in the catalog's discourse, which frequently references “data”, invites suggestions and comments (p. vii), starts with a User's Guide, accounts for the ephemerality of production and in its structure, which features far more indices and classifications than its predecessor, *Books in Print*.

2. Transmediality of production and reconfiguration of media ecosystem

The 1998 edition lists more than 4,000 actors—companies, organizations, and institutions—that were involved in the production of CD-ROMs. This list is strikingly diverse, ranging from universities (or conference organizers) and libraries to small firms specializing in adult content CD-ROMs, from government agencies and international scientific organizations to niche distributors, associations, and retail agencies, and from major tech giants to art galleries and media startups. For some of these entities, CD-ROM production represented only a small and temporary aspect of their broader activities. Others were established specifically for producing CD-ROMs, while yet another group transitioned into CD-ROM production from traditional publishing (Hachette, publishers in the field of law, specialized press in the economic sector, to name but a few), the audiovisual sector (Wizard, 20th Century Fox) or video disc media.

Moreover, this heterogeneous assembly of actors contributed at various stages of CD-ROM production, taking on roles such as content developers, data preparators, hardware manufacturers, mastering experts, search software creators. The guide thus provides an overview of the flow of CD-ROM production. It captures a moment when highly diverse players came together to shape the CD-ROM ecosystem. It also provides a snapshot of two parallel dynamics: the emergence of new actors shaped by CD-ROM technology (e.g., Eureka Electronic, a company born in 1991 and engaged in several activities such as distribution, content development, data preparation, mastering, consultancy, publication) and the adaptation of long-established institutions in publishing (e.g., Grolier, which then became part of the Lagardère Group, published the first encyclopedia on CD-ROM in 1985).

Other important elements are to be noted, particularly in the technical specifications of CD-ROMs: their use of Quick Time or other software, sound and memory specifications, compatibility with the PC or Macintosh systems, and the various formats parallel to the CD-ROM itself. For example, the CD-I or the FM-TOWNS system (p. 1275), focused on graphics and compatible with audio CDs, demonstrates other paths to transmediality and the challenges of standards and interoperability.

3. Transmediality of content

As both a product and a mirror of genre hybridity, *CD-ROMs in Print* showcases through the titles listed the intersections, overlaps, and hybridizations of media and genres that defined this period. The 1998 edition lists approximately 13,000 CD-ROM titles, presenting an impressive panorama of “re”- and “trans”-mediations. By navigating this landscape, we may retrace how content circulates across media forms, the functions that CD-ROMs fulfill in these processes, and the broader implications for late 1990s digital culture.

There are diverse manifestations and *uses* of transmediality within the CD-ROM medium. In some cases, CD-ROMs remediate content **to complement or extend** the original media source. For example, the CD-ROM *Conduct Unbecoming* (p.189) supplements Randy Shilts' eponymous book, providing not only full text but also interviews, over 2,000 photographs and documents, and profiles of hundreds of gay U.S. Military servicemembers. On contrary some cases demonstrate the complete **detachment of the content from its original form** (e.g., the CD-Rom *Adventure Bible*, p.12, where the players need to save Froggo, while relying on their knowledge of Bible facts and history).

Some CD-ROMs afford the **distribution and reuse** of materials, acting as intermediaries that allow text, photographs, and video to be repurposed across various media platforms (this is the case for many business CD-ROMs, which remediated and distributed reference lists, clip-art, photographs, such as *Business Metaphors and Details* (p.111)). In contrast, some CD-ROMs function as **archives** for otherwise “ephemeral” media, preserving content that might not survive in other formats (one fascinating example is the *AB20 Amiga*, which would deserve its own story, as a mirror of the vivid demoscene surrounding Amiga - the Amiga archive shutting down in April 1992 and being first preserved at the university of Berkeley⁴).

We may also mention cases of **radical genre and media hybridization**—such as the diverse forms of virtual museums on CD-ROMs, where the museum medium is remediated into various formats, from a static image collection to video games. Examples include *Ancient Egyptian-Art-The Brooklyn Museum* (1994) featuring 100 items with “multiple views and details of selected hieroglyphs and objects that are difficult to see during a museum visit” (p. 38) and *Versailles: A Game of Intrigue at the Court of Louis XIV* (1997) by the Réunion Des Musées Nationaux, a French cultural institution experimenting with what can be described as a “*serious game*”.

Finally, transmediality appears in its most reflective form when one medium is used to **mediate access to another medium**, as exemplified by CD-ROMs serving as gateways to the burgeoning world of the Internet (e.g., *Complete Internet Collection*, p.182, which includes Netscape Navigator, 15 Internet access hours, an interactive online shopping CD, and 10,000 BBS listings).

Through an exploration of this extensive catalog, we piece together an *entangled media story*, where different media, both analog and digital, not only coexist but reinforce and adapt, influence, and shape one another. While our focus is limited, the catalog opens many other avenues for further exploration, such as market segmentation or geographical distribution of production, which are of interest for the industrial and economic history of CD-ROMs. A distant reading of the catalog could also provide valuable insights, with, for instance, hundreds of occurrences of terms *multimedia* and *interactive*.

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⁴ https://wiki.preterhuman.net/AB20_Amiga_Archive_on_CDROM

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